

INDIAN EDUCATION 2020 AND ECONOMIC POLICY SEZLEADS TO UNDERMINE

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Introduction:

Economic and education policy are backbone of Indian society. It influences to all social category given by Indian Constitution. 85 % population is trodden by traditional books and its attitudes. Education and trade commerce is a major source to live standard life. It increase human index. Index of standard of living and having share in four pillars of democracy gives us status and direction and inspire us to move forward.

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Objectives of the Study

1. To know socio economic development through SEZ
2. To know new education policy 2020
3. To know the problems in economic and education policy
4. To suggest some remedies on problem

Research Methodology

The research paper is done along with , comparative study and analytical study through the various research papers, reports, books, journals, newspapers and online data bases, china's SEZ etc.

Indian Special Economic Zone

From 1951, India has accepted mix economy for development of financial and industrial through the five years plans. For promoting foreign trade and increases export, India has started first Free Trade Zone at Candela in 1965. Then in 1974 it expanded at Cochin, Mumbai, Chennai, Vishakha Pattanam and Surat. The progress and expansion of SEZ in China, Korea, Singapore, Malaysia and America has considered by Government of India and accepted the concept of SEZ in March, 2000. Then protection of exporters and demand of traders has been considered by Indian government. Parliament bill of SEZ has sanctioned on 23rd June, 2005 by the central government. SEZ Act has been applicable to all over India. SEZs are recognized under financial development and export promotion. As per SEZ Act, SEZ means specially created territory of free taxes and fees. In these sector industries are established for producing articles and supplying services. As per Special Economy Zone Act, 2005 and 2006, the definition of SEZ was included articles production, supplying services, free trade and free ware housing. Three types of SEZ is as under

- 1) SEZ for multi-products
- 2) SEZ for special sector
- 3) SEZ for port or airport

To declare by government, which type of SEZ has permitted out of above types of three?

Some of the economist and politician are explain SEZ as a way of economical development, but some of them oppose the SEZ. The well known economist Mr. RaghunathRajan said that the tax free facilities given to the SEZ, so give up revenue of the country. The social worker Mrs. MedhaPatkar says that the SEZ is only for self interest section. Mr. VishwanathPratapsing said that the government is helping the companies to take over the land from the farmers. The supporters of SEZ say that the SEZ has promoted and accelerated the development of economy, to increase infrastructure facilities, employment and export. For entrepreneurs included in SEZ have provided international trade services and amenities, in fractural facilities as well as financial promotion schemes, so they have obtained new life. This industrial sector is developed with trade centre, educational institutions, residences facilities as well as hospital, play grounds and entertainment centers are included. In new Mumbai SEZs are going to develop for increasing investment included electricity generation centers, transports facilities etc. so these SEZs are attraction to domestic and foreign investors.

Pros and Cons of Special Economic Zone:

Special economic zone have its pros and cons.

Some Pros of SEZ

1. Foreign market will gate to the Indian goods.
2. Export will be increased.
3. Deficit of Indian budget will be controlled
4. Easy entry in the market.
5. No any obstacle by the government
6. Decision making power totally come under the owner of SEZ.
7. Employment will be generated.
8. Foreign currency will be increased

Some Cons of SEZ

1. SEZ will be deemed as a foreign territory
2. Lot of losses through tax free scheme for next 15 years will be there.
3. Democracy will be sabotaged
4. Indian law will be removed from SEZ
5. Capital class will capture total economy of India.
6. Principle of socialism will be abolished
7. Exploitation of worker will be there.
8. Sc, st, obc and minority peoples will not be given job on first and third rank of position.
9. It creates capitalism.
10. Distance between poor and reach will be increased.

Special Economic Zone and FDI with Its Effects.

following problems will be created by SEZ

1. **Farmers are being made landless:** - In India, near about 70% of the population depend on farming. It is main source of their income. Because of SEZ many farmers become landless for taking lands from the farmers. Many amenities are giving to the farmers and they are ready to give their land to the SEZ and farmers will be landless. Then landless

- farmers, there is not available for income, some farmers are committing suicide.
2. **Foreign industries will capture Indian market:** this policy of FDI do not provide specific limitation to foreigner industrialist. Due to this, home industries and its product will be made out of market.
 3. **Unemployment problem will be increased:** - SEZ is a private property so that employment will be provided to the nearest capitalist class.
 4. **Medium and small scale industries in risk:** - Small and medium industries are the back bone of India. They are producing goods and services. Lot of industries is Indian. But due to sez, medium and small scale industries will have small scope.
 5. **Effect on agricultural sector:** - Due to SEZ, agriculture sector area will be reduced and production will also be reduced. Available agricultural production will not be sufficient to increase population. For this purpose agricultural grain will import.
 6. **Revenue loss of government:** -by providing tax free facility, the government and Reserve Bank are bearing lot of losses.
 7. **Capitalism abolishes the democracy:** -the system of sez help to increase the capitalism. The industrialist of the SEZ is providing various facilities; some of the industrialist will be take benefit. They will sales their product in fewer prices and creating monopoly.
 8. **Financial disequilibrium:** -The government is transferring their responsibility in industrial sector to the SEZ holders. Due to SEZ rich will become rich and poor will become poor. The gap of rich and poor will be increasing. For this reason, social dissatisfaction will occur.
 9. **Imbalance in environment:** - Large scale industries will establish in the SEZ. From these industries will mix unusable chemicals in the water and air and water and air pollution will be increased. The sound of big machinery in SEZ is creating sound pollution and environment will be imbalance.
 10. **No protection of the workers:** - The workers in the industries of SEZ, the worker laws will not be considered. For these reasons the industrialist will be doing increase working hours, close the work, lock-out, decrease the workers etc. and workers has no protection for their work. They will be unsatisfied about the work.

Pros and Cons of Education Policy:

Some pros of education policy

1. It will be modern education policy
2. It will give Equal opportunity to all
3. SC ST OBC will give equal treatment
4. Educational institution will get autonomous
5. I Std. to PG will be under observation of central educational policy maker

Some cons of education policy

1. It provides strengthen to upper class compare to OBC
2. It decrease OBC's percentage in education field
3. No any constitutional safeguard is provided to OBC
4. Process of share in power of OBC will be totally collapse
5. It is new hidden policy to undermine to 62 % OBC

6. It is a hidden policy to cut thumb of right hand like Yeklavya
7. It is nothing but use of 62% population of OBC to overcome power

Remedies for overcome problems

SEZ and FDI.

1. **Constitutional safeguard:** There should be constitutional safeguard and maintain OBCs status and direction
2. **To acquire non agricultural land for the SEZ:** - The non agricultural land should be acquired for SEZ.
3. **Limited scope to foreigner industrialist:** FDI has been open to all. Due to this, foreign countries will sabotage to Indian industries. So limited scope to foreign countries should be there like china's policies.
4. **Farmer share in SEZ:** Lot of land are used for agriculture by the farmers. Farmers should be given partnership of fifty fifty.
5. **SEZ should be come under the act and laws:** for SEZ, there is no any restrictions or control of the government. Company act 1956, negotiable instrument act, income tax act, GST etc. acts are not allowed to the SEZ. So it is not in favor to India. Indian economy will be wholly capitalist country.
6. **To save the Small Scale Industries:** - small scale industries create employment in large scale. If due to SEZ small scale industries will be closed, unemployment will increase. So list of the articles of small scale industries should be prepared, that will save small scale industries.
7. **Do not injustice on the farmers:** - The government should be taken care about the farmers whose land will be acquired. They should have share in FDI and SEZ.
8. **Acquisition of the land on lease:** - The land for FDI and SEZ should be given permission to SEZ holders, to take land on lease. The price of the land acquired for SEZ should be considered future price of land.
9. **To protect workers' rights:** - For protection of the workers right, workers laws and acts should be applied in the FDI SEZ projects.

Remedies for overcome problems

New Education Policy

1. There should be safeguard for 62 % OBC in new education policy
2. There should be adequate quota for OBC
3. Adequate representation in education policy making
4. There should be Empowerment policy towards OBC
5. Proper representation in four pillars of Democracy through new education policy

Conclusion:-

Economic and education policy are going to make more empowerment to upper class. It seems inclusive policy but it has its hidden agenda to under control 62 % OBC forever. Religious books and its owner manifested that OBCs are servicer of three varna that is Bramhin Kshatriya and Vaishya. They do not have right to take and give education, they do not have right to accumulate wealth, they do not have right to do any types of business and it is right only of Vaishya varna. Only rights of education was in the hand of first varna Brahmin. This was the policy of education and commerce towards huge population of OBC. Modern education and economic commerce policy is like new bottle but same vine.

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Hyderabad:

India Sold to Hindustan: MrBhalerao

Bhartatil Arth vyavastha : Dr. Bharat AsaramPagare, MTP Pune

PDF file by government: Education Policy 2020

www.sezindia.nic.in

Newspapers:

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Loksatta (Marathi)

Economic times